

Specific Aspects of the Church's Contribution to A Society's Development in the Past and Present

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ABSTRACT: 'Love for God' and 'love for all men,' which include 'the whole law and the prophets,' are constantly preached by the Christian Church. From its beginnings, the Church has contributed permanently to society by promoting a relationship based on love between people and nations, taught the people to live a disciplined life, guided them to the knowledge of God and His edification, to science, to culture, diligence, and other biblical values essential to human life. Therefore, this paper is meant as a reassessment of these values in the contemporary context.

KEY WORDS: Church, teaching, knowledge of God, Gospel, society development

Man: the Connecting Link Between Spirit and Matter

God, One in Being and three in Persons, is the Supreme Creator of the universe in all the glory of its harmonious diversity. The infinite goodness and Divine richness manifests in the creation of the universe, in its continuing support and governance through the uncreated divine energies, to participate in the richness of the IntraTrinity Divine love, in complete solidarity.¹

God is not just a cosmic clockmaker, who starts the mechanism and then lets it go on its own.² On the contrary, according to Saint John the Evangelist, creation is continuous, "My Father worketh hitherto; and I work."³ If God would not exercise His creative will at every moment, the universe would crumble, as the inspired Psalmist confesses, "All to You expect to give them their food at the right time. You giving them their will gather You opening Your hand, all will be filled with good things; But if You turned Your face away, they will be disturbed; take their spirit and they will end and will return to dust. Send Your spirit and they will be build and renew the face of the earth. The glory of the Lord forever! Rejoice the Lord in His works."⁴

Based on these realities, of God's permanent care for creation, we get to man and his relation to his Creator and the creation in which he lives. Man, as Olivier Clement says, goes through the life of this world looking at its unspoken depths; encounters mysteries everywhere and sees the reflection of other worlds. Nothing is closed in itself, nothing finished, nothing definitive fixed in this world. The world is transparent, its borders are always moving, it penetrates into other worlds and other worlds penetrate into it. There is no impenetrable opacity in the world.⁵ The created world is not isolated from man as well as it is not isolated from its Creator. It was created for man and through man it fulfills its purpose, namely "to share in the freedom of God's sons."⁶ Man, created to be born, grow, multiply and become perfect in nature, has the noble duty "*to interpret the book of nature*", to understand the universe in his marvelous structure in its harmony and to give it a rational articulation. Man is creation's archon and together they must reach the Creator of all. Nicodemus the Hagiorite testifies that man, in the contemplative prayer, brings forth to God the whole sensitive and intelligible world which he summarizes and contains within him as a micro cosmos.⁷

Man, the link between spirit and matter, is molded in the "image of God."⁸ The human being (body and soul), in collaboration with the divine grace which was in elementary state a fundamental dimension of his, aims to deify himself and with himself all creation, the entire kingdom that was created for him with this goal.⁹

The gracious state is man's state of harmony and communion with God, with himself and with the entire material and spiritual

creation. In this state all creation is characterized by that interior union of each with everything,¹⁰ and of the whole with God; the whole universe becomes a transparent medium of expression and manifestation of God.

The primordial harmony, existent through creation, tended normally, naturally, because of the uncreated divine energies in it and due to the cooperation of man with Divine Grace to reach perfection, in sustaining the good, the beautiful, in communion with God to glorify Him continually and thereby to forever share the Intra-Trinity Divine Love.

Alone man of all visible and thoughtful was built mortal and immortal, visible and invisible, sensible and understandable, seer of the visible creation, knowing of the thought.¹¹

Jesus Christ or the Man's Restoration

Man's natural, native state is the gracious state, constitutive to him since creation. God took dust from the ground and "formed man and breathed into his face the breath of life and made him a living being."¹² The Holy Fathers state that *once with the breath of life, God has also given man divine grace.*

After the Fall, *the image of God* in man was altered, the original gracious state was altered but not completely destroyed. Immediately after the expulsion from paradise after the punishment, man receives the promise of a Redeemer who restores the possibility of regaining the gracious state and will objectively rise to the maximum approach to God.¹³

The Incarnate Son of God, after His Resurrection, blows again on the Apostles, gives them the grace to work with God to the "creatio nova" which is just beginning, new creation in which man is restored, objectively saved by God.

St. Cyril says: "The Holy Spirit was given to first man together with life". His action was inside the man. As a result of the Fall, the Spirit's work becomes exterior to nature. Afterwards man is in a fallen state, and therefore only the love of God can restore man through His Son.

“In the fullness of time,”¹⁴ when the world was ready for the coming of the Savior, the divine grace was given to man by God-Man in full. Incarnation, Passion, Resurrection,¹⁵ Ascension and sending the Holy Spirit into the world to make the presence of Christ in His Church real until the end of time bring all people the divine grace, the objective salvation that each one and all in the spirit of love and communion with Christ must appropriate it.¹⁶

In the baptismal consecration of Jordan, the Holy Spirit is placed on the human nature of Christ and from Pentecost becomes a worker from within human nature. The effect is the vitality and effectiveness of the force with which the Apostles preached unto death compared with the fear before this moment.¹⁷

Church-Pentecost Continued to Earth

The church is the body of Christ, is the continued Pentecost on earth, is the image of the Trinity, the absolute Church of the three divine Persons. The church can be understood only by experience, by grace, through participation in its liturgical life, “Come and see!”¹⁸

Holy Apostles John¹⁹ and Peter²⁰ talk about “the Lamb sacrificed since the world began,” which shows that the act of creating the world, carries in itself, beforehand, the Saints Community in Church, as the alpha and omega of any of God’s creative *iconomy*. The confession of faith places the beginning of the Church in Heaven. God “came in the cool of the evening,”²¹ to talk to the man: thus the essence of the Church is pictured in the bond between God and man; foreshadowed in the Edenic state, prophetically anticipated in the Old Covenant ordinance, it is fulfilled in the incarnation and puts forth the Celestial City,²² the living Church of the Lamb’s wedding. The Holy Fathers bring forth the greatest fact of divine philanthropy: God is made man, and thus It unites through marriage, which is created with what is uncreated. Jesus Christ, the God-Man, by extension due to the principle of consubstantiality, becomes Christ - the Church: God - humanity, divine-human fullness.²³

Beyond the image of the world that is transient, faith reveals the permanent act that does not change: the world’s destinies and

each other's are intertwined at the level of the Church, from this predetermined center of the universe. Man is saved in the Church, which means according to St. Peter that "he participates in God's nature."²⁴ Deified humanity thus depicts the living "imitation" of the Trinity: the unity of human nature in the multiplicity of its hypostases. The theology of the Church, in its scale, especially highlights the universal participation in the divine life conditions: the integrity of nature and its immortality.²⁵

Specifics of the Church's Past Contribution to Social Development

God has permanent care of His creation, renewing it in His spirit: "Send Your spirit and will be build and You will renew the face of the earth."²⁶ The incarnate Son of God, entrusted the Holy Apostles and their successors, the threefold ministry (teaching, sanctifying and ruling): "Wherefore, going and teach all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit, teaching them to observe all things whatsoever I have commanded you, and lo, I am with you in all days, until the end of the world. Amen."²⁷

Moreover, under the universal priesthood basis, every Christian is responsible and obliged to his peers to preach through word, prayer and good deeds which he received in turn from God through the sacramental priesthood or universal: "And you are a chosen generation, a royal priesthood, a holy nation, a people earned by God, that *you may proclaim to the world the greatness of Him* who called you out of darkness into His glorious light, you who once were not a people, and now you are God's people; you who once had no mercy, and now you have mercy."²⁸

Church teaching is applicable in daily life and touches all aspects of life. To gain an insight into the Church's contribution to society's development in the past, I will list some key aspects for human life.

In full slavery period, in which people were regarded as mere possessions and could be sold, bought by the wealthy, and the general

population was content if it had bread and circuses (the most popular being the gladiatorial fights—they fought until one of them died in the arena), behold the Savior teaching to love all people, including the enemy takes shape and is taught, often by blood of the martyrs. This huge leap was made from the human dignity of Christianity, every human being in “God’s image,”²⁹ with the purpose of reaching deification. Moreover, Christ identifies with each of us “I was hungry and you gave Me food; I was thirsty and you gave Me drink; I was a stranger and you took Me in; I was naked and you clothed Me; I was sick and you took care of Me; I was in prison and you came to Me.”³⁰

The woman received a new dignity in Christianity. They are the ones who Christ revealed Himself to after His resurrection from the dead and they proclaimed the apostles. More women are mentioned as Lidia³¹ who was baptized together with her household, “a woman named Damaris,”³² who believed the words of St. Paul etc. Continuing this path, girls began to go to school and be active in society.

The first schools were set up in the Church’s porch. Here studied future ministers of the Holy Shrines, deacons, readers, copyists of manuscripts etc. I exemplify the stated with the school inside the Princely Church in Curtea de Argeş. There appear many graphite inscriptions: “here I am, I signed on my own accord, Gabratin”, dated before 1369, probably names of craftsmen who worked on building the church. Mircea the Great certainly had in Curtea de Argeş, a “grammar school” where the teacher and scribe Michael studied, who recorded at 10 June 1415 a document issued by the prince at Argeş: “I Michael grammarist, <I wrote> in Arghiş, July 10th in the year 6923 141 and indiction 8, during the time when Mustafa Celapi came.”³³

Moreover, the first industrial schools were also set up by servants of the Church, renowned craftsmen making decorations, monumental projects—mostly churches and monasteries, sacred objects (Crosses, carved book covers, embroidery etc.)

The first books transcribed by copyists and after the invention of printing, printed with the methods of the time, were also in the Church setting. The 1508 printed books are well known in present day Romania: *Missal* (1508), *Octoihul* (1510) and the *Four Gospels* (1512).

The first hospitals were built also around Churches. The famous Vasiliade, founded by St. Basil the Great (IV century) were spread throughout the Christian world in present day Romania being near the strongest centers and being called “Bolnițe”—designation exists even today in some Churches, such as the Church near Curtea de Argeș monastery.

Civil legislation was Christianized, certain pagan provisions being eliminated over time, like the death penalty.

Over time hierarchs were close advisers of kings but also helped with diplomatic missions, mediation of certain conflicts and misunderstandings etc., they were part of the Royal Council, took the place of the King when he was gone, etc, all of these because they were highly educated men and well trained. Romanian Country rulers, along with the hierarchs who consecrated their rule and guided them and the people in good faith to Christ, were followers of the best Roman and Byzantine traditions. After the fall of Constantinople to the Turks (1453), Romanian Country rulers and hierarchs were those who preserved and supported the Orthodox Church both in the country and throughout the whole Orthodox world of the time. Examples are Radu the Great and Neagoe Basarab. About last, Gabriel the Priest wrote: *“in all sides from the East to the West and from Noon to Night, all holy churches he fed and showed much mercy everywhere. And wasn’t only good to Christians, but also to the pagans, and was a merciful father to all, resembling the heavenly Lord, who shines His sun and rains on the righteous and on the wicked, as shown by the Gospel.”*³⁴ Therefore it is justified the claim of historian Nicolae Iorga that the Romanian Country was successor of the Byzantine heritage, being a true *“Byzantium after Byzantium.”* Moreover, in Romanian Country the cultural heritage of the Byzantine Empire bloomed and brought forth a culture, an art and an Orthodox Christian life specific to Romanians.

The Christian Church has always urged to knowledge: *“And this is eternal life: that they may know You, the only true God, and Jesus Christ whom Thou hast sent;”*³⁵ to knowledge and skill in all aspects of life, from the words of Sacred Scripture: *“Leave the unwise to stay alive and walk on the right path of understanding!”*³⁶

Through the religious education but cultural and social that the Holy Church ministers give parishioners of all kinds, through

preaching, catechesis, public and private discussions, participate in a harmonious development of society.

Education, in the fullness of the word, is the most precious heritage that we can acquire or give as legacy to our children, grandchildren and our fellow men, its fruits returning to those who give it and bearing hundredfold fruit, today and forever. I base these affirmations on the Word of Life in the Holy Scripture ("what you sow, so shall you reap"³⁷), on the experience of humanity synthesized in history (nations who had a sound education both in theory and applied in real life day endured most - and I mention here our ancestors, the Dacians, for which culture, education and religious life were essential, educated people, as a percentage, it is reached only in modern times by us,³⁸ the applicability in everyday life is visible in the family care - as shown by scenes from Trajan's Column in which captive Dacians protect their little ones and their wives) but also on own experience.³⁹ Through education, we take the fruits of the Holy Spirit, the sap wisdom gained by predecessors, preparing us at the same time to go through the future: "*Hear the instruction, to get wise!*"⁴⁰

"What is a man profited, if he shall gain the whole world, and lose his own soul? Or what shall a man give in exchange for his soul?"⁴¹

With this question begins the Catechism, or the Foundations of Faith. It's a question that at first glance, is related to religion, very few even among believers taking it seriously. Let's briefly take a look at this question's connotations that our Savior Jesus Christ asks, starting from the root of human life, ie at the stage of infancy and childhood.

Most of us, bodily or spiritual parents, we do our best for our bodily children or our spiritual children. Often we endure many to provide them whatever they need, to not want of anything, to be happy, to have, as the saying goes, everything we lacked. This is the general mentality. But what is the biggest dowry that we can give to children and our fellow men?

The answer has to do with the human being in its complexity, body and soul. The most precious dowry is faith (here we understand

our love for God and others and the whole building of God), education, acquiring wisdom, understanding, harmony and all deep values.

Let me illustrate with a reality described in the Holy Scripture and continued in the Holy Tradition. It is about the rich man who came to Jesus and asked him what to do to gain eternal life. After he testified that from childhood he fulfilled all the words in the Law, the Savior told him to sell all he has to divide it to the poor, and follow Him and thus be complete. The young man saddened, says the Scripture because he was rich. From the Holy Tradition we learn what happened next! He continued living as before, and when the Romans destroyed Jerusalem leaving not one stone upon another, he realized the words of the Savior and their absolute validity.

This experience of the young man in the Gospel, rich in material things, is had by any rich man in material things, who gives material wealth to children, relatives, but doesn't also offer spiritual riches, which are part of the human soul, the result being well known. How many wealthy individuals do not keep their children in luxury, pampering them with everything, how many people do not give fabulous fortunes to their followers but without preparing them not crush by them, how many people who gained fabulous sums overnight have reached how they got. What is the explanation? We find in it the people: *Where the mind is not, woe is the foot.*

Analyzing these we understand better about the profound values that we can give to those we love and care about. Material dowry has its role, is pleasing to God, but spiritual heritage is fundamental to the life of our peers.

What has all this got to do with preaching the Gospel to the younger generation? I will summarize a few key dimensions:

a. Prayers and religious knowledge essential to the Christian life. Their role is essential. Great scholars, academicians, laureates of various international awards have reached the certainty of the existence of a Creator and testified in their works, as reason has guided them to God. Arriving here they grew in knowledge but also in the joy of life. The reverse? What happened with many celebrities who have gained the whole world (known everywhere, with colossal fortunes, with everything we can imagine) but they came to drug addiction, psychological treatments, reaching to suicidal gestures.

The explanation is simple. Man is composed of body and soul, and if he is fed only materially then he becomes unfortunate, he is unbalanced. The believer at any time of life, even in moments when he feels overwhelmed by certain situations, persecuted or even tortured, he retains his balance and even joy for having communion with Christ, the Son of God Incarnate, he is certain that this life is fleeting and full happiness waits for him. So I was happy to see believers who survived the tortures and persecutions with dignity, with prayer and could have a tremendous emotional balance. When we trust in ourselves and in our wallet, as a fragile mentality does, we would crash at any imbalance together with our wallet. Who has God the Father, as we say in the Lord's Prayer—Our Father, whatever the situation is under the protection of the Heavenly Father that does not allow temptation greater than the power and the help that He offers His sons and daughters.

Hold On to What You Promised Yourself Into!

Steadfastness in the vocation we have. It was during my most beautiful days in college when I read from the Wisdom of Jesus son of Sirach: "Hold what you promised yourself and occupy yourself into that fully up and rejoice, and fully enhance your work. . . . Trust in the Lord and stay fully in thy labor. . . . The blessing of the Lord is the reward of the believer and in an hour rather raises His blessing."⁴² I confess that in many moments of life this wisdom, and many others, which we hear in sermons in Church, at spiritual evenings, round meals, symposiums etc., helped me to be mentally balanced and live my life more than anything else. We learn a lot and forget a lot. Counts, as wisdom says, that remains after we forget. What it means to be operated on by career doctor, who does it from the passion and has made it all his life? What it means a career priest who serves fondly even if he cannot live from it and is forced to work something else to support his family or to support his priestly mission? What it means a career teacher who educates children without thinking how much is valued or paid by the society, with the awareness that his pupil may be tomorrow's neurosurgeon who will operate on his brain. This is

the difference between having and not having a religious education. Another significant aspect! In difficult moments in life when you realize your own limitations and the inability of those around you, communion with God is the only way that gives you hopes of healing, raising, salvation from the hardships of life.

What You Sow; So Shall You Reap!

a) If we baptized the children and feed them physically, we also need to feed them spiritually and to care for their training in the complexity of the human being. Education is human being's food, and the religious dimension is basis, the journey but also the finality of man's forming. I objectify this with the model of Professor Alexandru Ionescu, God rest him with the righteous. He tutored us all for admission to college. His Lordship House was a true cultural-educational center (is my model and I wish to be a teacher), all rooms were occupied by his or his wife's disciples. His children were not given a great material dowry but gave them spiritual food and cultural heritage and God helped them all to become great men, with families and everything they need, and Ms. Ionescu, the children's mother, got to see the world with the help of who was the mother of both bodily and spiritual. How much difference between the Christian family and those receiving all for granted and not knowing to appreciate anything! At the end of college, His Eminence Father Calinic, Hierarch of Arges and Muscel, asked us something different: "What is everyone's favorite verse?" Finally, the verse that we put to heart was: "*Be not deceived: God will not be mocked; for what you sow, so shall you reap.*"⁴³ Here then, after more than 15 years have passed since, what does religious education received from individuals dedicated to serving God mean. We forgot a lot, but some were printed and bear fruit, with the help of God, in our hearts.

b) Respect for parents, grandparents and all fellow men: "God said, 'Honor your father and your mother.'⁴⁴ Parents who encourage children to take both religion class in school and to also go to Church services, actually support and honor themselves, ensuring that they will be respected by their children and other children who will be

tomorrow's young and a little later will be the next generation of doctors, teachers, mayors, priests, etc. What is more rewarding for a parent in old age than to see his children worshiping him? Where is this taught? At Church, at the Religion class, at spiritual evenings and reading books useful to the body and soul.

c) Learn to do good deeds to fellow men, with the assurance that God identifies with them. *"As you did it to one of these too small brothers of Mine, You have done it to Me."*⁴⁵ What could be more important for a parent, grandparent, and a normal person than to contribute after means and prowess to the pursuit of this goal? This is the pinnacle of education and good growth. Be polite, do good deeds, to be forgiving, to rejoice even when someone does or says something bad to you.

d) Providing spiritual and physical health for the children. Through religious education they are taught to discern right from wrong, thus acknowledging the disaster of sins materialized in various deeds or vices: drinking, smoking, drugs, prostitution, depression etc. How expensive is this?

By Giving, You Shall Acquire!

e) They have the consciousness link between helping others and salvation. *"He who turned the sinner from the error of his way will save his soul from death, and shall cover the multitude of sins."*⁴⁶ So an essential work of every Christian in life is to be an apostle of religious education both at school and in the Church and society. Let's think about the value of this aspect. The wise man sowing grain having the best seeds to have a blessed harvest, also gives seeds to his neighbors. Along with the religious aspect - God multiplies and rewards—is a material aspect—if the neighbors all have good seeds they avoid the danger of interbreeding and cultural degradation due neighborhood with inferior kinds. Thus we have the awareness that spiritual advantage also implies material advantage, since the Lord is the Possessor of the spiritual world and the material one, the two are interdependent.

All of us have experienced the joy of faith in different factual circumstances of our lives or our relatives, this feeling reminding me of the words of Nicholas Stainhard “giving you acquire” and the wisdom of historian Nicolae Iorga: “Wisdom is yours only when you share it with another, otherwise it is just in you.”

God bless us with joy, faith, hope, wisdom, steadfastness in the best and, above all, to help us bring forth in us the love, which according to the counsel of St. John the Evangelist, is immortal, it is eternal because “*God is love and he who remains in love remains in God and God in him.*”⁴⁷

NOTES

¹ Dumitru Stăniloae, *Teologia Dogmatică Ortodoxă*, Vol. I, (București: Editura Institutului Biblic și de Misiune al Bisericii Ortodoxe Române, 1996), 287.

² Daniel Gligore, *Sacerdoțiul omului. Omul-preot al creației* (Curtea de Argeș: Editura Dacpress, 2004), 7.

³ John 5:17

⁴ Ps 103:28–32

⁵ Dumitru Stăniloae, *Ascetica și Mistica Ortodoxă*, Vol. II (Alba Iulia: Editura Deisis, 1993), 18.

⁶ Rom 8:21

⁷ Nichifor Crainic, *Sfințenia împlinirea umanului*, Colecția „Teologie și Spiritualitate” Nr. 2, (Iași: Editura Mitropoliei Moldovei și Bucovinei, Trinitas, 1993), 164.

⁸ Genesis 1:26–27

⁹ Gligore, 2004, 13.

¹⁰ Vladimir Soloviov, *Fundamentele spirituale ale vieții*, Traducere de Diac. Ioan I. Ică (Alba Iulia: Editura Deisis, 1994), 88.

¹¹ Ion Bria, *Tratat de Teologie Dogmatică și Ecumenică*, Colecția Didaskalos (București: Editura România Creștină, 1999), 107.

¹² Gen 2:7

¹³ Gen 3:15

¹⁴ Gal 4:4

¹⁵ Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, “Fie ca învierea lui Iisus să ne schimbe inima și să ne mărească credința!” în *Argeșul ortodox*, Săptămânal teologic, bisericesc și de atitudine al Arhiepiscopiei Argeșului și Muscelului, Curtea de Argeș, anul XI, nr. 546, 25 aprilie–2 mai (2012): 5.

¹⁶ Gligore, 2004, 37

¹⁷ Paul Evdochimov, *Ortodoxia*, Traducere de Irineu Ioan Popa (București: Editura Institutului Biblic și de Misiune al Bisericii Ortodoxe Române, 1996), 159.

¹⁸ Ibid., 135.

- ¹⁹ Rev. 13:1–8
²⁰ 1 Peter 1:19
²¹ Gen 3:8
²² Rev 21:22
²³ Evdochimov, 1996, 137.
²⁴ 2 Peter 1:4
²⁵ Evdochimov, 1996, 137.
²⁶ Ps 103:31
²⁷ Mt 28:19–20
²⁸ I Peter 2:9–10
²⁹ Gen 1:27
³⁰ Mat 25:35–36
³¹ Acts 16:14
³² Acts 17:34
³³ *DRH, B, Țara Românească*, vol. I, doc. 38, p. 80-82.
³⁴ This information comes from a brief note recorded during the seventeenth century by a monk Gavriil the Elder of the Holy Mount Athos in reference to Neagoe Basarab. Cf. *Sfântul Neagoe Basarab, voievodul Țării Românești – Argumente pentru canonizare, Tropar, Condac, Sinaxar, Slujba și Acatistul* (Curtea de Argeș: Editura Episcopiei Argeșului și Muscelului, 2009), 8.
³⁵ John 17:3
³⁶ Solomon 9:6.
³⁷ Gal 6:7
³⁸ Mihai Bărbulescu, „Învățământul (literatura, filosofia, mitologia, dreptul roman, medicina, matematica),” in Dumitru Protase, Alexandru Suceveanu, eds., *Istoria românilor, Daco-romani, Romanici, Alogeni*, vol. II, (București: Editura Enciclopedică, 2001), 228.
³⁹ Eliza Milcă, „Din cuvântările Preotului Daniel Gligore, „Educația și roadele ei. Astăzi și în veci,” in *Bucuria Credinței*, nr. 2/ (2015-2016): 42.
⁴⁰ Solomon 8:33
⁴¹ Mat 16:26
⁴² Wisdom 11:21–24
⁴³ Gal 6:7
⁴⁴ Mat 15:4
⁴⁵ Mat 25:40
⁴⁶ James 5:20
⁴⁷ 1 John 4:16